

EFFECT OF BASALT FIBRE HYBRIDIZATION ON HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to investigate the effect of basalt fibre hybridization on carbon/epoxy laminates when subjected to high velocity impacts. Four different stacking configurations are studied in order to assess the effect of different lay-ups on impact resistance.

Two hybrid configurations are manufactured: in the first one (BCBS) fabrics are stacked as a sandwich-like sequence with carbon fibres as a core and basalt fibres as skins, while in the second configuration (CBCS) the core is made of basalt fibres and the skins of carbon fibres. Not hybridized basalt (B) and carbon (C) composites are also manufactured as reference configurations.

The response to high velocity impact tests is assessed through the evaluation of the impact and residual velocities of the projectile and the ballistic limit, calculated using experimental data, is compared with the results given by an analytical method, showing a good agreement. The damage in composite laminates is investigated by destructive (optical microscopy) and non-destructive (ultrasonic phased array) techniques. In addition to high velocity impact tests, also three-point bending tests are performed on undamaged specimens.

As a result of basalt hybridization, the ballistic limits of all sandwich configurations are enhanced if compared to those of carbon laminates. Therefore the observed decrease of static mechanical properties, namely flexural strength and modulus, of hybrid composites seems to be largely compensated by improved response to impact. Advantages also come in terms of cost saving, since the basalt fibre is far less expensive than the carbon one.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composite materials are increasingly gaining importance in many high technology fields of engineering, in particular for aeronautical structures because of their high specific strength and stiffness [1-5].

A key issue of composite laminates used in aeronautical field is their resistance to low and high velocity impact. Various impacts by foreign objects are to be expected during the service life of the aircraft. During the production assembly and maintenance operation, tools can be dropped onto fuselage panels. Hailstorm and collision with debris during take-off are another source of damage.

However, the toughness of carbon fibre is quite low and the resulting impact damage resistance is poor. In this regard, one traditional approach to improve the impact resistance of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) is through hybridization with more ductile fibres such as for example glass or aramid ones. Glass fibres are the best option from the viewpoint of cost, availability and ease of processing, and hybrid carbon/glass fibre composites have consistently demonstrated better damage tolerance under impact than their carbon fibre counterparts [6-8]. There has been a number of experimental and numerical studies on the perforation behaviour of a wide variety of polymer composite laminates. Abrate [3-4] reviewed research in low-velocity and ballistic impact of laminated composite materials. Cantwell and Morton [9-11] studied damage mechanism of a number of carbon fibre reinforced composite laminates under low and high velocity impact loading. Ballistic impact tends to produce greater levels of damage and therefore larger reductions in residual tensile strength. Bland and Dear [12] reported a broad set of experimental results of projectiles impacting carbon-fibre reinforced polymers, and a qualitative analysis of the different types of failure resulting from these regimes. Caprino et al. [13] performed ballistic tests on CFRP panels of different thickness and used the results to verify the analytical models previously proposed by Wen [14] and by Cantwell and Morton [11]. Both models proved to be reliable to predict the perforation energy as a function of target thickness.

Recent researches have shown that basalt fibres have mechanical properties comparable with those of traditional glass ones in addition exhibiting advantages in terms of environmental sustainability and chemico-physical properties. Mineral fibres obtained from basalt rocks are not new, but their suitability as reinforcement in polymer composites is a relatively new issue [15]. The elastic modulus of basalt fibres strongly depends on the chemical composition but it is usually comparable or slightly higher than that of glass fibres, while both tensile strength and elongation at break are higher [16]. These properties suggest the potential role of basalt fibres in replacing glass ones as impact resistance improver for composite laminates with also a view to enhancing the environmental sustainability of such composites.

More recent researches have confirmed that composites hybridised with basalt fibres allow to improve the response to low velocity impact tests [17] but no study was found dealing with their resistance to high velocity impacts.

The aim of this work is to assess the role of basalt fibres in enhancing the high velocity impact response of carbon/epoxy composites. To achieve this objective, also the influence of the basalt fibres on the static behaviour was analysed. High velocity impact tests have been performed on four different stacking configurations in order to assess the effect of different lay-ups on impact resistance. From the experimental data, the ballistic limit velocity and the absorbed energy are determined. Also an analytical model is used to predict the ballistic limit of these composites. The composite damage was evaluated by C-scan ultrasonic technique and by cutting the specimen along a transverse plane containing the projectile path.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The composite panels have been produced by autoclave forming using plain weave basalt (200 g/m²) and carbon fibre (160 g/m²) reinforced epoxy prepregs supplied by DeltaPreg (Italy).

Two hybrid configurations have been manufactured: in the first one (BCBS) fabrics are stacked as a sandwich-like sequence with eighteen carbon fibre layers (core) and seven basalt fibre layers (skins) for each side of the laminate, while in the second configuration (CBCS) twenty layers of basalt fabrics as core and five of carbon fabrics as skins are used. Not hybridized basalt (B) with twenty-five layers and carbon (C) with thirty-two layers have been also manufactured as reference configurations. Details of all the composite types are reported in Table 1.

Composite type	Thickness (mm)	Fibre volume fraction
C	4.00±0.04	0.58±0.02
B	4.00±0.05	0.64±0.01
CBCS	4.00±0.05	0.63±0.01
BCBS	4.40±0.06	0.61±0.01

Table 1: Thickness and fibre volume fraction of the tested laminates.

Three-point bending tests have been performed on five specimens, with dimensions of 100 mm × 25 mm, for each configuration in accordance with ASTM D 6272. These tests were performed in a Zwick/Roell Z010 universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell using a span-to-depth ratio of 16:1 and a cross-head speed of 2.5 mm/min and a pre-load of 3 N. Displacement transducer has been employed to measure the effective strain and to evaluate the flexural modulus.

The high velocity impact tests have been performed on twelve specimens for each configuration using a helium gas-gun test set up with a spherical tempered steel projectile (mass = 1.725 g, diameter = 7.5 mm) over a range of impact energies until complete perforation of the target is achieved.

Samples of dimensions 100 mm × 100 mm are used. The sample is mounted in a simply supported boundary condition along its edges by aluminium guides. To measure impact and residual velocity, a high speed digital camera, with a data acquisition system capable of taking 36000 frames per second, is placed beside the impact chamber. For better recording quality, a high intensity halogen light has been used. The velocities are calculated from the evaluation of the distance travelled by the projectile in several consecutive frames recorded by the camera.

After determining the velocities of the projectile before and after impact using the high speed camera, the experimental data have been fitted by least-square regression according to the classical Lambert-Jonas' equation [18] to obtain the ballistic limit velocity.

The impacted specimens have been scanned using non-destructive ultrasonic inspection equipment OmniScan MX with standard phased array probe 3.5 MHz, linear array, 64 elements. All the laminates have been subjected to ultrasonic non-destructive evaluation both before and after impact testing. The ultrasonic testing before impact loading is carried out to ensure that there were no fabrication defects in the sample. Post impact testing was conducted to get information about the extent of damage in the sample.

Finally the specimens have been cut with a diamond saw along a transverse plane containing the projectile path. Images of this section have been captured with an optical microscope, allowing the analysis of the different failure mechanisms.

At the end an analytical model to study the impact process of a spherical projectile penetrating at high velocity is applied. This model is derived from energy balance relationship and is based on the assumption that during a ballistic event, deformations are localized and that the mean pressure provided by a composite to resist a projectile consists of two parts: (i) the cohesive quasi-static resistive pressure as a result of elastic-plastic deformation and (ii) the dynamic resistive pressure arising from velocity effects. The ballistic limit of each configuration is then predicted using Wen's perforation model [19-20]. In this model it is assumed that the cohesive static resistive pressure is equal to the static linear elastic compression limit (σ_e) in through-the-thickness of the composites.

The ballistic limit is given by equation 1:

$$V_b = \frac{\pi \Gamma \sqrt{\rho_i \sigma_e} D^2 T}{4m} \left[1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{8m}{\pi \Gamma^2 \rho_i D^2 T}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where ρ_i and T represent the density and the thickness of the composites, m and D represent the mass and diameter of the projectile, respectively. The term Γ is an experimentally-determined constant with a value of 1.5 for hemispherical-ended projectile and σ_e is the elastic limit of the composite in through-the-thickness compression.

The compression behaviour of the composites is determined through a series of in through-thickness compression tests performed in a servo hydraulic testing machine with a crosshead displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min according to ASTM D 695 and at least five specimens of each material have been tested to obtain reliable data. Specimens with dimensions of 10 × 10 mm have been cut from the panels and the load vs. deformation is recorded during each test. The σ_c of the specimens is determined at the knee (change of slope) in the stress-strain curve.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 summarizes the results from flexural tests (flexural strength and flexural modulus) and experimental ballistic limit calculations. It is clear a hierarchy in terms of flexural performance.

Composite type	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Ballistic limit velocity (m/s)
C	782.02±9.16	47.01±1.37	174
B	629.48±22.71	29.80±1.82	285
CBCS	675.22±24.25	43.91±2.16	244
BCBS	768.97±1.94	34.41±0.15	230

Table 2: Flexural data (avg. and standard deviation) and ballistic limit velocities.

The basalt fibre hybridization affects the flexural strength and modulus of laminates. Carbon composites (C) are stiffer than basalt (B) ones due to the higher elastic modulus of carbon fibres. Flexural tests on specimens highlight that hybrid composites have flexural stiffness intermediate between those of carbon and basalt ones. The different lay-up of the hybrid composites plays an important role on the laminate stiffness.

In fact, B and BCBS hybrid configurations present a more gradual failure process (Figure 1). This has been related to the fact that in the BCB sandwich structure, the outer layers, responsible for bearing the bending load, are made of basalt (less stiff than carbon). Hybridization also provides improved flexural strength. C composites show a higher flexural strength than B ones but hybridized configurations allow to strongly improve both flexural strength and toughness compared to carbon laminates, and the sandwich configuration with basalt fibre skins seems to represent the best compromise between these two competing requirements. This behaviour has been related to the higher number of carbon layers in the BCBS configuration, characterized by a higher ultimate strength than basalt ones.

Figure 1: Typical stress-strain curves obtained from flexural tests.

As regards the ballistic impact, after determining the velocities of the projectile before and after impact using the high-speed camera, the incident projectile impact velocity is plotted versus the residual velocity for each configuration as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Residual velocity vs Impact velocity for all configurations.

Due to the difficulty of controlling impact velocities precisely and the existence of a zone of mixed results in which a projectile may completely perforate or only partially penetrate under apparently identical conditions, the ballistic limit could not be calculated in a deterministic way [21]. In this work the ballistic limit has been estimated by fitting an equation to the experimental data by the least-squares method. The fitting curves (solid lines) shown in Figure 2 have been calculated using the Lambert-Jonas model [18] that relates residual velocity to impact velocity by means of the following equation:

$$V_R = A(V_0^p - V_{BL}^p)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (2)$$

where V_0 is the impact velocity of the projectile, V_{BL} the ballistic limit, V_R the residual velocity of the projectile, and A and p are empirical parameters. In this study, the value of p , V_{BL} and A are estimated by a least square fitting method. The predictions from the model follow the general trend of the experimental results for all configurations (Figure 3). However, the model overestimates the ballistic limit by as much as 15%. The difference in magnitude between the model and the experiments can be attributed to model hypotheses about the specific failure mechanism, weave architecture and the boundary conditions. The elastic limit of the laminates in through-thickness compression also needs a better investigation for the studied carbon/basalt composite panels in order to closer predict the ballistic limit.

From experimental ballistic data (Table 2) basalt confirms the best behaviour to impulsive loads already highlighted in the case of low-velocity impacts [17]. Due to the greater toughness of the basalt fibre compared to carbon fibre, the B composites show the highest ballistic limit velocity. On the other hand, the tests highlight once again the brittle behaviour of the laminates reinforced with carbon fibres. The morphology of impact damage shows significant differences in terms of impact response (Figure 4). Basalt composites showed extensive debonding phenomena around the hole caused by the projectile. It is possible that the higher value of ballistic limit for basalt composite is also ascribed to the ability to dissipate energy through failure phenomena at the matrix/fibre interface. In the case of C composites, the energy dissipation occurs mainly through brittle failures in fibres and matrix as shown by the net entry hole and a rear surface of the composite mainly characterized by splitting. The positive effect played by basalt is also evident in the hybrid configurations that are all characterized by a ballistic limit higher than that of carbon composite. The sandwich configurations BCBS and CBCS

are characterized by a damage pattern highly dependent on the skin type (Figure 5) and resemble the failure mechanisms previously observed for B and C composites. It is important to observe that the CBCS configuration is the one that shows the highest value of ballistic limit also having carbon skins. This is due to the fact that the laminate CBCS is the configuration that has the highest basalt fibre volume fraction.

Figure 3: Predicted and experimental ballistic limit velocity for all configurations.

Figure 4: Front and back face damage of basalt and carbon composites beyond the ballistic limit velocity with the corresponding C-Scan image.

Figure 5: Front and back face damage of hybrid BCBS and CBCS composites beyond the ballistic limit velocity with the corresponding C-Scan image.

In order to characterize the samples, it has been also evaluated the energy absorbed in the process of perforation (Figure 6). The energy absorbed by C composites decreases rapidly with increasing impact energy. In B composites the decrease of the absorbed energy as a function of the impact energy is less pronounced, thus confirming the excellent dissipation energy properties of this material. Hybridization has a fundamental role on the energy absorption. In fact hybrid composites containing basalt, regardless of their configuration, have shown a considerable increase of the energy absorption, making their impact response much more similar to that of B composites.

Figure 6: Absorbed Energy vs Impact Energy for all configurations.

Figure 7 reports typical examples of longitudinally sectioned impacted composites below and above the ballistic limit velocity for each lay-up sequence. C composites impacted below ballistic limit show a conically-shaped shear zone whilst in the lower half of the coupon the fibres appear to have fractured in a tensile manner with the presence of delaminations. For C composites impacted above ballistic limit, the projectile begins to penetrate the uppermost plies through a shearing process and when it reaches the delaminated layers they begin to slide relatively to each other and ultimately fail

when the local stress directly in front of the projectile reaches the failure stress of the fibres.

B composites show in the front side a damage similar to a hole having a diameter nearly equal to projectile diameter. Delamination area is also small and circular in shape, around the hole; the reason is that when the projectile impacts on composite laminates initially up to certain thickness of laminate, material surrounding the projectile will undergo compression-shear failure mode and for the remaining thickness of the plate, it will undergo tension-shear failure mode, which is responsible for delamination and matrix cracking on the back side of the composite laminate.

The sandwich configurations BCBS and CBCS are characterized by a damage pattern highly dependent on the skin type and resemble the failure mechanisms previously observed for B and C composites. In the sandwich configurations the skin at the tension side is still undamaged thus no full penetration was observed below ballistic limit. During the ballistic test above ballistic limit the skins both at impact side and tension side are damaged and full penetration is observed. Delamination was found to play an important role in sandwich configurations due to the presence of dissimilar layers. This can be due to the fact that the interfacial forces between dissimilar layers are weaker compared to that of similar ones. This is particularly evident for BCBS composites below ballistic limit where complete delamination within the lower skin causes the full ejection of the basalt skin. In CBCS the shear out and related compression of material ahead of the penetrator is limited by the basalt core thus delaying the growth and development of extensive delamination.

Figure 7: Fractographs of sectioned composites after ballistic impact conducted at various velocities.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of basalt fibre hybridization on high velocity impact response of carbon fabric reinforced epoxy composites have been experimentally investigated.

From the experimental results the following conclusions can be drawn:

- All configurations containing basalt fibres have demonstrated a higher ballistic limit velocity than that of carbon composite. Also the absorbed energy is higher for all impact velocities analysed. Thus the addition of basalt increases the impact behaviour of carbon composites.
- Basalt composites showed damage pattern characterized primarily by debonding, while in the case of carbon configuration the fracture is brittle, with obvious signs of splitting. The greater toughness of basalt fibres can be the reason of the different ballistic behavior found;
- As a whole, CBCS laminate compared to C laminate shows a percentage decrease of flexural strength and modulus of 14% and 7%, respectively but a gain in terms of ballistic impact of 40%, making it the best compromise between static and high velocity impact properties.

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